

ODESSA

Deliverable D2

D1.1.2 - Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

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D4 Report on Communication, Dissemination and exploitation of project results	
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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document presents ODESSA Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan, defining the actions and implementation measures envisioned to efficiently communicate about project objectives and activities and disseminate its outputs in order to ensure the best exploitation of results.

The document outlines the key messages which are to be considered in all communications issued by all partners, and provides an analysis of the stakeholders to whom these messages are directed and the channels identified for their delivery. This Dissemination and Exploitation Plan sets out communication activities designed to ensure that all relevant and interested stakeholders are involved and/or reached, and properly, correctly and regularly informed and kept updated.

The principal aim of the Dissemination and Exploitation plan is to inform and engage the wider stakeholder community. The main objectives of the plan are:

- To raise awareness of ODESSA objectives and foster stakeholder engagement;
- To ensure regular information flow of ODESSA progress and results to the relevant stakeholders.

The dissemination activities will follow the different phases of the project. During the start-up phase the communication activities will be focused in creating the graphical identity and in promoting the ODESSA objectives in the Stakeholder community. The key tasks of this phase will be:

- the creation of graphical identity (project logo, project website, ...)
- the identification of key stakeholders and potential end-users of ODESSA outputs including specific EU Institutions, industry, relevant scientific networks, regulatory bodies
- the identification of communications means (academic journals, specialised magazines, workshops and events)
- the development of communication and dissemination tools and key messages tailored to the specific stakeholder groups.

During the Project Implementation phase, the focus will be on dissemination of the results of the project, and exploration of opportunities for sustained exploitation of results.

The main tasks during this phase are:

- preparation of communication and dissemination material (Flyers, brochures, posters, ...)
- publication of articles on world-class academic journals and specialised magazines
- participation in trade fairs and other industry events.

During the closure of ODESSA project the focus will be on the preparation of recommendations regarding the future development of the project and the results exploitation.

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ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

CA: Consortium Agreement
CNRS: Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique
CS2: Clean Sky 2
EC: European Community
EP: Exploitation Plan
EU: European Union
IC: InterConsulting
IP: Intellectual Property
IPR: Intellectual Property Rights
IST: InnoSenT GmbH
JU: Joint Undertaking
KPI: Key Performance Indicator
LRU: Line Replaceable Unit
MS: Micro Soft
MSS: Modular Surveillance System
ODESSA: Obstacle DEtection Sensor for Surveillance on Aircraft
SLB: SiraLAB
SME: Small Medium Enterprise
SW: SoftWare
TAWS: Terrain Awareness and Warning System
TBC: To Be Confirmed
TCAS: Traffic Collision Avoidance System
TM: Topic Manager
UAV: Unmanned Air Vehicle
URL: Uniform Resource Locator

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Scope and objectives

This deliverable is the first of two deliverables regarding the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan of ODESSA project.

This first deliverable (M6) includes formulation of ODESSA project Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation strategy and an action plan for these activities.

The second deliverable D4 (M24) will include a detailed report of the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation activities performed in the project.

The Dissemination plan in ODESSA project represents the strategic vision of the Consortium in terms of communication of the ODESSA project itself, and of its achievements and outputs as well.

The main objective of the activities is to increase the visibility of the ODESSA project on selected communities and target groups at both European and International level and to further facilitate the realization of the impacts. In order to maximize impact, special attention will be given to specific stakeholder groups such as (i) researchers, (ii) small aircraft manufacturing industries, (iii) avionic system industries, automotive industries (iv) and (v) aeronautical regulatory bodies.

This deliverable outlines the ODESSA dissemination strategy in terms of identification and description of the dissemination key elements:

- the objectives of the dissemination (mission, vision),
- the subjects of dissemination (what will be disseminated),
- the target audience (to who it will be disseminated), as well as
- the dissemination methods (how it will be disseminated),
- the distribution of responsibilities for dissemination (who will perform the dissemination) and rules for planning and performing of dissemination activities are described here.

The Consortium attaches great importance to dissemination. All partners will contribute to that effort.

The Exploitation Plan (EP) outlines the expected exploitation of project results and IPR management.

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1.2. Document Overview

Chapter	Contents
Chapter 1	Introduction, <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Scope and objectives• Document Overview
Chapter 2	Applicable documents
Chapter 3	Dissemination Strategy
Chapter 4	Exploitation Plan
Chapter 5	Conclusions

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2. APPLICABLE DOCUMENTS

- [1] GRANT AGREEMENT:** Grant Agreement number: 821263 - ODESSA — H2020-CS2-CFP07-2017-02
- [2] INTERNAL CONSORTIUM AGREEMENT:** To be finalized
- [3] PROJECT MANAGEMENT PLAN:** DLV 05 – D1.1.5 Project Management Plan Ref N° DLV05-000684-A Rev1

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3. DISSEMINATION STRATEGY

The objective of the dissemination strategy is to identify and organise the activities to be performed in order to maximise the influence of the project and to promote commercial and other exploitation of the project results.

In more detail, the objectives of the dissemination are:

- To raise public awareness about the project, its expected results and progress within defined target groups using effective communication means and tools;
- To exchange experience with projects and groups working in the field in order to join efforts, minimize duplication and maximize potential;
- To disseminate the fundamental knowledge, the methodologies and technologies developed during the project;
- To pave the way for a successful commercial and non-commercial exploitation of the project outcomes.

The dissemination strategy and activities will follow principles and best practices tested by the partners in other projects and in line with the EC Guidelines for successful dissemination:

- All research results/reports will be duly reviewed and a copy will be sent to relevant partners involved in the project before these are published or disseminated.
- All consortium members who will contribute to the project activities will be duly informed about the final outcomes and the implications stemming from project results.
- All public results will be accessible and usable from all parties who may benefit from them.

The definition of the dissemination strategy is based on the identification of the following points:

- the subject of dissemination (what will be disseminated),
- the identification of target audience (who will most benefit from the project results and who would be interested in learning about the project findings),
- the definition of methods and tools (what is the most effective way to reach the target audience),
- the timing (when dissemination will take place),
- the dissemination management and policy (who is responsible of and how dissemination is ruled).

3.1. Subject of Dissemination

The following general subjects of dissemination have been identified:

- ODESSA project itself (general scope, coverage, goals and milestones and plans to reach them)
- Interim and final results (reached objectives and achievements)
- Techniques and methodologies (in respect of IPR Issues)
- Technologies (in respect of industrial IPR Issues)
- Innovation aspects

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3.2. Target Audience

The overall aim is to maximize the utilization of the dissemination potential of ODESSA consortium.

Dissemination activities then must be tailored in such a way to reach the audiences most efficiently through appropriately selected dissemination channels and dissemination tools.

One of the key elements of the ODESSA dissemination strategy is the identification of dissemination target areas and audiences.

3.2.1. Dissemination within the ODESSA Partners (Internal Dissemination)

Ensuring effective internal communication and dissemination among the Consortium partners represents an important element for the ODESSA Project.

Partners' organizations are important for dissemination for two reasons. First, they are potential users of ODESSA project results themselves and secondly they represent "influencers" because of their impact on the associated industrial sectors.

In this respect, the dissemination activities rely on the effort and the possibility of each partner in exploiting opportunities to present the project and its result. Therefore, it is important to communicate information about ODESSA project and its results to partners' management, consultants and people responsible for their marketing and sales. Additionally, it is necessary to encourage them to share this information further to their customers and business partners.

Methods of internal dissemination can vary from providing links from partners' web pages to the ODESSA website, to seminars or workshops showcasing, to articles in partners' internal newsletters and publications etc.

The internal communication strategy also pursues the objective to maintain all partners fully informed about planning, work in progress and existing or potential problems.

Documents and files for internal communication can be uploaded on the Project Repository and website.

3.2.2. Dissemination beyond the ODESSA Partners (External Dissemination)

In order to structure the external dissemination activities in the dissemination plan and to be able to analyse the impact of dissemination on a comparable basis a more accurate division of the target audience was developed in the following table.

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Type of Audience	Motivation
Academic and research community	This group targets all research communities interested in the ODESSA project's developments, results and innovation which can be beneficiary for their own research activities. Scientific contributions of ODESSA are particularly interesting for researchers working in the field of development of anti-collision technologies, obstacle detection and identification, sensor fusion, Modular Surveillance System, Antenna Design
Small Aircraft (general aviation, ultralight, UAV) manufacturer	This group targets all the manufacturers of small aircraft, UAVs, business jets, interested in improving aircraft safety during take-off and landing and taxing phases, integrating, by a quite small investment, an obstacle detection system scalable, modular and ease to integrate
Avionic Systems manufacturer	This group targets all the avionics systems manufacturing interested in anti-collision systems, in scalable and modular avionic systems and in porting of automotive technologies into aeronautic sector
Automotive Industries	This group targets all the automotive industries interested in porting of automotive technologies in aeronautics
International/ National Regulatory Bodies	Regulatory bodies should be aware of ODESSA scope and objectives, owing the innovative character of the developed technologies. Their involvement is useful to provide consultative advice on pre-standardization procedures which may be carried out when the technology reaches a suitable readiness level.
EU projects working in similar domain	To share results and innovation

Table 1. Segmentation of ODESSA external audience

External dissemination will address the defined target groups at national, European and international level. As ODESSA received funding from the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, the EU is naturally interested in the project results being disseminated at EU and worldwide level.

3.3. Dissemination activity timing

The dissemination activities are to be performed according to the following logical schedule:

- 1. Initial awareness phase (month 0-6):** this especially includes establishment of ODESSA graphical identity (i.e. project logo, project website,..) and analysis of relevant information resources in terms of identification of dissemination means and opportunities.
- 2. Targeted dissemination phase (month 7-18):** the consortium will enrich the website, produce the communication KIT (Flyers, brochures, posters, presentations,). Preliminary project results will be presented to the target audiences, publishing articles and attending to identified events and workshops.
- 3. Closure phase (month 18-24):** this represents the period closely before the end of the project, when ODESSA consortium partners will start preparation of recommendations regarding the future development of the project and the results exploitation.

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3.4. Dissemination management

3.4.1. Distribution of Responsibilities

According to the Article 29.1 of the Grant Agreement “Each beneficiary must – as soon as possible – ‘disseminate’ its results by disclosing them to the public by appropriate means (other than those resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including in scientific publications (in any medium).”

Therefore, every possible opportunity will be embraced by individual partners or on collective basis through joint appearance by more than one partner to make ODESSA known among technicians and general public as well.

All partners of the consortium must contribute to the dissemination according to their foreseen role and effort and using all available tools. Thus for instance by participating and giving presentations at conferences, publishing papers, attending to events, networking and similar activities and will strive to maximize the existing dissemination channels for the purpose of project results dissemination.

In particular the following Roles and responsibilities have been identified:

Activity	Responsible	Contribution	Notes
Definition of dissemination plan	IC	All	
Preparation of dissemination KIT	IC	All	
Publications	All	All	CNRS Responsible for Scientific Publications
Participation to events and workshop	All	All	
Dissemination Report	IC	All	

Table 2. Dissemination Roles and responsibility

The following focal points for dissemination activities have been identified for each partner:

Partner	Focal Point	Reference
CNRS	J.Y. Dauvignac	e-mail: jean-yves.dauvignac@unice.fr phone: +33 (0) 489 154 425
IC	S. Maddaluno	e-mail: s.maddaluno@inter-consulting.it phone: +39 06 41204467 - 219
IST	Thilo Lenhard/ Patrick Wolz	e-mail: thilo.lenhard@innosent.de/ patrick.wolz@innosent.de phone: +49 9528 9518 51/ +49 9528 9518 1271
SLB	Chiara Silveri	e-mail: chiara.silveri@siralab.com phone: +39 0744243179

Table 3. Dissemination Focal Points

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3.4.2. Dissemination policy and rules

The dissemination of the project outcomes and any publications should respect the agreed dissemination of each consortium partner's foreground, IP and data. The use of foreground and its restrictions is stipulated within the Internal Consortium Agreement, any data provided by any third parties will be subject to restrictions within a non-disclosure agreement. To ensure that a party's intellectual property is protected, notice of any publication must be given to the Project Coordinator at least 45 calendar days before publication, this will then be circulated to all partners. Any partner then has 30 calendar days to raise an objection to the publication. Objections are justified if the protection of the objecting Party's results or background would be adversely affected or the objecting Party's academic or commercial interests would be significantly harmed. The objecting Party must make a precise request for necessary modifications.

In the event an objection is raised the party proposing the publication and the partner objecting will seek to find a solution on a timely basis and the objecting Party shall not unreasonably continue the opposition if appropriate measures are taken following the discussion.

Any publications or dissemination activity should also be reported to the Project Manager for logging and for inclusion in the dissemination report (Deliverable D4).

All external communications must acknowledge the EC funding in the following way:

“This project has received funding from the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 821263 “

Moreover the ODESSA Logo, the JU Logo and the EC emblem must be displayed.

3.4.3. Dissemination Kit

The Dissemination Kit is a public instrument that can be used for communication/dissemination purposes without asking prior advice on contents, but project partners are always required to inform the Project Manager about the specific channel where the KIT will be used (Event, articles, conferences, meetings, social media) in order to log and include it in the dissemination report (Deliverable D4).

3.4.4. Dissemination monitoring and reporting

All consortium partners are encouraged by the partner responsible for dissemination (IC) to report the results of each dissemination activity immediately after they are presented. The reports shall include feedback gathered by the respective partner from the target audience (if applicable), eventually gained contacts to be used for further dissemination purposes.

All partners are invited to publish the dissemination material on the Project Repository (this can be a paper, a conference presentation, video, ...).

For monitoring purposes, the dissemination activities will be reassessed regularly by the Project Manager during the project progress meetings.

The information gathered during the entire lasting period will be analysed and will be included in the planned Dissemination Report (Deliverable D4).

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Moreover the Interim and the Final reports to be delivered to EC for Interim and final reviews must also include details on dissemination and exploitation activities.

3.4.5. Evaluation

For the purposes of evaluation of ODESSA dissemination activities, the following key performance indicators (KPI) have been defined to measure the impact of the dissemination and communication activities carried out by the project consortium from the project start (Table 4).

These KPI will be periodically reviewed by the Project Manager in collaboration with the whole Consortium.

Dissemination Channel/ Tools	Key Performance Indicators (KPI)	Expected Results (M24)
Project Website	Number of visits	500
Social Media (Linkedin, Twitter)	Number of followers Number of tweets	250 followers 50 tweets
Poster/ Flyers	Number of Brochure/ Flyers distributed	1000
Publications	Number of publication	5
Attendance of events	Number of events attended	4

Table 4. Key Performance Indicators and expected results

3.5. Dissemination Tools

3.5.1. Graphic Identity LOGO

The logo includes the name of the project (ODESSA) - its main concept intends to capture the attention of the audience.

The LOGO will be used for any (internal or external) deliverable, report and dissemination tool.

Figure 1. Odessa Logo – Colored and printable versions

3.5.2. Project Flyer

The main objective of the project Flyer is to provide our audiences with an attractive and written project overview and a summary of the main project objectives and characteristics. To assist the dissemination effort, the flyer will be published on the project website.

The flyer will present the goals of the project and the main (expected) findings. The text will be designed taking into account not only experts, but also an interested non-specialist audience.

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Furthermore, it will include the website address and provides basic information on ODESSA Consortium. All partners' logos will also be displayed.

3.5.3. Project Poster

The main purpose of the poster is to catch the audience attention. The poster focuses on the visual aspects.

The content of the poster has to be clear and easily understandable by the target audience. With regard to the layout and design, the poster will show the ODESSA project's logo, and a graphic reminding to the project product.

From the content point of view, the poster of the ODESSA project will illustrate its objectives and include basic information on the project and on the Consortium, including all partners' logos. It will be possible to download it from the ODESSA website.

3.5.4. Project Website

Project websites are one of the main communication tools of projects.

To ensure maximum visibility to the ODESSA objectives and results, it will be set up a project website registered in the "eu" domain and with an intuitive URL to increase hit rates.

The design of the website will build upon the following criteria and taking into account suggestions given in the EU Project Websites – Best Practice Guidelines (EC, 2010):

- **visual communication:** use of colors and/or photos, web pages are easy to browse, information is kept short and links are included to websites, publications, and so on.
- **verbal communication:** the website uses simple phrasing, no jargon is used in order to attract the widest possible audience.
- **visibility:** maximum use of free or affordable methods to increase page ranking on search engines,
- **webmaster Tools** provided by search engines to check indexing status, good cross-linking between the different pages of the site and other sites, add keywords to the web page metadata; use frequently used keyword search phrases both in the metadata and in the contents pages.
- **regular update of contents:** the website is maintained by Dissemination focal points and the update will be regularly done by the Webmaster upon inputs of partners.
- **monitoring tools:** the website will include a counter of visitors or other statistical tools that will be used to measure the number of visits.

3.5.4.1. Public Website

The public section of the ODESSA website will:

- provide a brief project summary highlighting the objectives, the contents and the structure of the ODESSA Project including the composition of the ODESSA Consortium.
- provide a short profile of each of the ODESSA Partners and a link to its web sites;
- provide access to the project Publications
- provide copies of publications and presentations done at conferences/ workshops in various formats (pdf, MSWord, etc.);
- feature a *news* section with the latest information related to the project, and an *events* section that will show the events to which the ODESSA Project will attend to
- HOME: the home page of the website shortly will introduce the ODESSA project and will give the important relevant information.

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The funding will be duly acknowledged, also by the inclusion of the relevant logos (i.e. EU, Clean Sky 2), and claiming that " *This project has received funding from the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 821263*".

The Homepage will contain links to all the following subpages (at least):

- Home: on this pages are described the challenge being addressed, the project objectives, an outline of the methodology, and the expected results and impacts.
- Partners (Consortium): this webpage section presents a brief description of the project partners, their logos and the links to the respective websites.
- Events: this provides a calendar that presents future and past events. It provides dates and a contact points
- Contacts: this section enables people to easily get in touch with relevant contact people of the project Consortium.
- Social Networks buttons: direct access to the social media (Twitter, LinkedIn)

3.5.4.2. Private Area

On the ODESSA website homepage there will be a link allowing accessing the private collaborative repository used for partnership internal communication and project management. The collaborative repository will be totally private and a password will be mandatory to gain access to it.

The Repository will support the following activities:

- Project progresses controlling
- Resources and Costs controlling and reporting
- Report management and preparation
- Deliverable monitoring and management
- Document management
- Contacts management, electronic mailing (to individuals or mailing lists) and messaging.

3.5.5. *Social Media*

In order to reach a broad target audience while establishing two-ways communication channels, the presence of the ODESSA project in social media will be one of the key actions for dissemination activities.

ODESSA will be registered in standard platforms like:

- **Twitter:** a Twitter page will be created as one dissemination instrument for reaching the general public (<https://www.twitter.com>). Relevant Twitter groups will be identified and approached for taking part in ODESSA activities.
- **LinkedIn:** A LinkedIn group (<http://www.linkedin.com>) will be created as one dissemination instrument for reaching stakeholders and industry professionals.

The website will have direct access to these social networks by clicking over the icons situated on the footer part of the website. In this way, it will be easy for every user to participate in this when the website is visited.

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3.6. Dissemination Activities

3.6.1. Dissemination Plan

All partners will contribute to maximize use of all dissemination channels, such as high quality papers containing the best scientific achievements and oral and poster contributions to topical international and European conferences. Industrial partners will regularly participate in workshops, fairs and showcases where technical achievements and prototypes can be shown to stakeholders. A list of major events has been identified and they will be up-dated during the project duration.

Dissemination Tools	Target Audience			
	Scientific Community	Industry/SMEs	Regulatory Bodies	Public at large
Project Website	✓	✓	✓	✓
Project Material (posters, flyers, videos,..)	✓	✓	✓	✓
Publications	✓	✓	✓	✗
Participation in events (workshops, trade fairs, ..)	✓	✓	✓	✗

Table 5. ODESSA Dissemination Tools and target audience

3.6.2. Target Publications

The Industrial and academic partners will individually and in collaboration publish and present scientific advances in technical papers as well as in journals and specialized magazines.

Scientific publications are an effective way to disseminate high level project information and to attract the interest of representatives of the various target groups.

Publications in specialized magazines, papers sent to related events will attract the attention of technicians and researchers as well as to give the opportunity to collaborate within the purposes of ODESSA. In order to support this activity, whenever possible, project publications will be archived or linked on the ODESSA website.

The following journals and magazines are especially relevant for the communication strategy of the project:

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Kind of Publication (Web/ Paper)	Details	Country (if applicable)	Website (if applicable)
Scientific/ Technical Journals	IEEE Transaction on Antennas and Propagation		
	Microwave and Optical Technology Letters		
Industry Magazines	TBC		

Table 6. ODESSA Target Publications (Paper/ Web)

3.6.3. Target Conferences and events

National and international conferences are an excellent opportunity to share the results with experts in the field and, therefore, to achieve an effective dissemination of the project.

Workshops, meetings and other large events (exhibitions, trade fairs, showcases) represent relevant opportunities for dissemination. The goal of these events will be to disseminate both the techniques developed during the project and the preliminary results of the project to the targeted beneficiaries of the ODESSA project. The following Table presents a brief description of the major international events where dissemination actions could be undertaken to publicize findings and innovations from the project.

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Kind of event	Event	Description	Frequency
Relevant conferences and workshop	IEEE/AIAA 36th Digital Avionics Systems Conference	Meeting of the Digital Avionics Systems Conference continues its history as the industry leading avionics conference distinctive for its dual focus on both avionics and air traffic management.	Every year
	Aviation Electronics Europe	International workshop on aerospace system technologies, which includes as topics: - Avionics - Flight Operations	Every year
	Radar Conference	International Radar Conference	Every year
	EuRAD and Conference	European Radar Conference (is part of European Microwave week)	Every year
Relevant fairs and events	Salon international de l'aéronautique et de l'espace de Paris-Le Bourget	It is the largest Air Show before UK's Farnborough and provides demonstration of the latest technologies in aerospace world.	Every two years
	Farnborough International Airshow	The airshow is an important event in the international aerospace and defense industry calendar, providing an opportunity to demonstrate civilian and military aerospace technologies to potential customers and investors	Every two years
	European Microwave Week	European Microwave Week is an internationally renowned event on microwave technologies. The event offers a platform for dialogue between participants on topics related to microwave, RF, and wireless technologies as well as defense and security systems.	Every year
	Aerodays	Aerodays is the European flagship event in aviation research and innovation. The event acts as a positive enabler for industry, governments, the European Commission, research institutions, academia and many others to come together to present strategic perspectives and achievements in aviation research and innovation.	Every four years
	Aerospace and Defence Meetings	Aerospace & Defense Meetings is a Business Convention for the Aerospace and Defense Industry. The event offers a series of side workshops and conferences on the reality of the sector with professionals from all over the world.	Every year

Table 7. Major International Event for project outcomes dissemination

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4. EXPLOITATION PLAN

4.1. Expected exploitation of projects results

The ODESSA Project aims to develop a low-cost Modular Surveillance System with highly scalable capabilities.

The project's outcome will prepare the path for the Consortium partners towards industrialization of an innovative multi-platform anti-collision system with resulting cost saving, greener technology, weight savings and reduction of the aircraft life-cycle cost, all increasing present safety level in low-altitude flight and taxing procedures.

This will contribute to provide the European industry with the technology innovation necessary to increase competitiveness in the global market not related to US suppliers.

Successful implementation of the project will lead to validated procedures in industrial practice for the design of millimeter radar and their feasibility, with fewer possibilities of errors or shortcomings, hence improving the overall reliability, maintainability and availability of the aircraft.

Interconsulting will use the developments under this program to establish a position as one of the leading suppliers of turnkey solution for avionic systems. The results of this project will also add additional benefits, promoting Interconsulting current product range of avionic systems, actually mainly set for Research Aircraft market, by expanding Interconsulting also into the Small Aircraft & Commuters market.

From **InnoSenT** side, instead two different results will be achieved: enforcing its leader position in advanced automotive sensors and bridging automotive technologies in aerospace field.

CNRS LEAT laboratory, instead, will increase its experience in European R&D programs increasing its industry collaboration network.

From **Siralab's** side, exploitation of activities from this project is expected to further strengthen its position as one of the well-recognized suppliers of unmanned aerial system from national to European landscape.

A detailed overview is proposed in the following table.

This will meet the CS2 objective of strengthening the European SME supply chain. The expected results show a real business opportunity mainly addressed to IC as System Integrator with the partners as sub-contractors.

The achievement of turnovers for 1MEuros in three years could justify the start-up of an internal line of business and additional investment in terms of human resources (n.1 for sales and n.2 technicians) and productive line (machinery and instruments)

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Partner	Planned use of project results	Timetable for use ¹	Estimated market size & potential (€)
IC	<p><u>Knowledge:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Avionic systems design -Computing anti-collision algorithm realization -Porting of automotive system in aeronautics -Integration of avionic systems in the A/C; mechanical installation, electrical integration, interface with other LRUs; -Testing according to required timing and scheduling performance. -Methodology and technology for avionic systems design. <p><u>Business:</u></p> <p>Extending company business in European aerospace landscape for activities in design, development and validation.</p> <p>Technology transfer and participation in regional, national and European projects, extending internal acquired knowledge for company business purposes.</p> <p>Since IC has all competences and qualifications for certification, IC will be the ideal partner for computing node’s design, development and certification.</p>	C	<p>The potential business can be estimated in 20K euros per ODESSA sensor delivered.</p> <p>An annual budget would be the sales of 20 up to 50 ODESSA sensors installation achieved in three years. For a total budget of 400Keuros to 1 MEuros in 3 years.</p>

¹ Commercial or higher TRL. C: Continuous, S: Single Shot

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“This project has received funding from the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 821263”

Partner	Planned use of project results	Timetable for use ¹	Estimated market size & potential (€)
IST	<p><u>Knowledge:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Avionic systems design - Porting of automotive system in aeronautics - Certification aspect <p><u>Business:</u></p> <p>InnoSenT business landscape will be enlarged in aeronautics system design, learning avionics system certification life cycle process</p>	C	<p>The potential business can be estimated in 4K euros per ODESSA system delivered.</p> <p>According to the previous sales estimation 200Keuros per Year could be reached in 3 years.</p> <p>Other collaboration could produce additionally 100Keuros per year</p>
SLB	<p><u>Knowledge:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Anti-collision system on board integration <p><u>Business:</u></p> <p>Siralab business will be enriched with participation to European program. Since Siralab works on home automation too, the collaboration with InnoSenT could help in business development</p>	C	<p>A royalty plan could be shared with SLB on the sales of ODESSA sensor equipment. The partnership with sensor developer and the flight trials services are</p> <p>estimated in 100K euro per year.</p>

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Partner	Planned use of project results	Timetable for use ¹	Estimated market size & potential (€)
CNRS	<u>Knowledge:</u> - Anti-collision system experience increasing <u>Business:</u> Partnership with private industries has an important role for research centre. ODESSA consortium could be a starting point for other collaboration.	S	N/A

Table 8. Expected Exploitation

4.2. IPR Management

The management of IPR is strictly ruled by the Internal Consortium Agreement (CA) which includes all provisions related to the management of IPR including ownership, protection and publication of knowledge, access rights to knowledge and pre-existing know-how as well as questions of confidentiality, liability and dispute settlement.

In the Internal CA the Partners have identified the background knowledge included and excluded.

The Internal CA regulates the ownership of results (Section 8 of the Internal CA).

The knowledge acquired in the course of the project shall be considered as a property of the partner generating it, and in this sense the originator is entitled to use and to license such right without any financial compensation to the other contributors.

In case of joint ownership of results, each of the joint owners shall be entitled to use their jointly owned results free of charge, but with written information (to avoid conflict of interest), and without requiring the prior consent of the other joint-owner(s) for their own direct Exploitation only.

As long as the joint ownership agreement is not yet concluded, each of the joint owners shall be entitled to grant non-exclusive licenses to third parties, without any right to sub-license, subject to the following condition:

- at least 45 days prior notice must be given to the other joint owner(s);
- Fair and Reasonable compensation must be provided to the other joint owner(s).

The Internal CA also regulates the transfer of results ownership (Section 8.3 of the Internal CA).

Each Party may transfer ownership of its results wholly or in part following the procedures of the Relevant Grant Agreement article 30.

It may identify specific "potential assignees" it intends to transfer the ownership of its results to in Attachment 6 to Internal CA.

The other Parties shall not object to a transfer to listed "potential assignees" in Attachment 6.

The transferring Party shall, however, notify the other Parties of such transfer and shall ensure that the rights of the other Parties will not be affected by such transfer.

Any addition to Attachment 6 after signature of Internal CA requires the agreement amendment procedure.

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5. CONCLUSIONS

The strategy outlined above aims at fostering the maximization of ODESSA expected impacts.

The dissemination strategy has been defined, identifying the dissemination subject, the target audience, the dissemination tools, the activities to be performed, their timing and management.

Moreover the document describes the expected exploitation of project results and the IPR management.

This Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation plan is a live document, subject to continuous update, following the progress of the project and its results.

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